

**EFFECTIVE AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF RECURRENT
PILONIDAL SINUS USING KSHARSUTRA: A SINGLE CASE REPORT****¹Dr. Ravindra Kumar Patil, ²Dr. Mukesh Pathak, ³Dr. H. P. Sharma**

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Article Received on 15 Nov. 2025,
Article Revised on 05 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 15 Dec. 2025,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17951419>

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How to cite this Article: 1*Dr. Ravindra Kumar Patil, 2Dr. Mukesh Pathak, 3Dr. H.P. Sharma. (2025). EFFECTIVE AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF RECURRENT PILONIDAL SINUS USING KSHARSUTRA: A SINGLE CASE REPORT. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 14(24), 957-960.

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ABSTRACT

Pilonidal sinus (PNS) is a chronic inflammatory disorder occurring in the intergluteal (natal) cleft, most commonly affecting young adult males. The condition often causes pain, sero-purulent discharge, embarrassment, work absenteeism, and considerable psychological distress. Conventional surgical procedures such as excision with primary closure or flap reconstruction are frequently adopted for recurrent or chronic cases; however, they are associated with prolonged hospitalization, postoperative complications, high recurrence rates, and increased treatment expenditure. In Ayurvedic literature, pilonidal sinus closely resembles Shalyaja Nadi Vrana, for which Ksarasūtra therapy is described as a minimally invasive and effective para-surgical procedure. It combines the benefits of drainage, debridement, and chemical cauterization, facilitating simultaneous cutting and healing of the tract with minimal recurrence. This case report presents a

32-year-old male with recurrent pilonidal sinus following a failed other treatment. The patient was managed with Ksarasutra therapy along with supportive Ayurvedic oral medication. Complete wound healing was achieved within one month without hospitalization, and the patient was able to continue his routine activities throughout the treatment. No recurrence

was observed during a 6 month follow-up period. The outcome suggests that Ksharsutra therapy may serve as a safe, cost-effective, and cosmetically acceptable alternative to conventional surgery in recurrent pilonidal sinus cases, offering quicker recovery and preventing recurrence.

KEYWORD: Pilonidal sinus, Nadi Vrana chikitsa, Kshar Sutra.

INTRODUCTION

A Pilonidal sinus is a sinus track which commonly contains hair. It occurs under the skin between the buttocks (the natal cleft) at a short distance above the anus. The sinus track goes in a vertical direction between the buttocks. Most cases occur in young male adults. The origin of Pilonidal disease is not fully understood, although hormonal imbalance, presence of hair, friction and infection are often implicated.^[1] The most commonly used therapy is surgery including wide excision and healing by secondary intention. However, post operative recurrence following surgery is high, leading to frequent and time-consuming wound care. Hence, there is a need to evaluate the role of the other alternative/ innovative techniques for the management of this challenging disease so as to minimise recurrence, make it cost effective, with improved acceptability & minimum hospitalization. The 'Sushrut Samhita',^[2] describes a condition 'Shalyaj Nadi Vran' which is similar to 'Pilonidal sinus'. 'Shalyaj nadi vran' is a track which is described to be due to presence of pus, fibrosed unhealthy tissue & hair etc. inside left unnoticed. Sushruta has advocated a very unique minimally invasive treatment i.e. 'Kshar Sutra' procedure for management of Nadi vran (PNS).

CASE REPORT

A 32year old male patient age, came to the Surgery O.P.D at Shalya Tantra, Pt. Khushilal Sharma Government Ayurveda College and Institute, Bhopal (M.P.), with complaints of recurrent discharge from a boil over an operated site along with pain and discomfort in 8 month and this was confirmed by MRI. The patient was not willing for surgery and requested Ayurvedic treatment. Hence, Kshar Sutra procedure was offered. Before planning treatment other etiologies like Tuberculosis, Pelvic inflammation causing abscess, HIV, diabetes mellitus, foreign body or trauma were ruled out. After confirmation of the pilonidal sinus by MRI, the two external openings were excised under local anesthesia and the embedded hair follicles were removed [Figure 1]. The KsharSutra was tied covering the entire underlying track for simultaneous cutting and healing [Figure 2]. Appropriate dressing was given under aseptic conditions. The patient was discharged on the day after the procedure. Patient was

asked to attend surgical clinic for dressing on alternate days. Seitz bath (hip) with lukewarm water was advocated before dressing. The KsharSutra was changed weekly for 3 sittings [Figure. 3]. To promote healing and reduce pain & inflammation oral antibiotics, anti-inflammatory drugs and multi vitamins were also prescribed. The tracks cut through and simultaneously healed by 4 weeks [Figure. 4]. However, it was observed that healing rate was slow compare to cutting rate and the patient was observed for a period of 6 Month to check for recurrence.

Kshar Sutra is a medicated thread (seton) coated with herbal Alkaline drugs like Apamarga (Kshar) (Ash of *Achyranthus aspera*), Snuhi (*Euphorbia neruifolia*) latex and Haridra (*Curcuma longa*) powder in a specific order. This combination of medicines on the thread helps in debridement and lysis of tissues, exerts antifungal, anti bacterial, and anti inflammatory. Another mechanism proposed for the KsharaSutra is that it destroys the residual glands in the epithelium.

DISCUSSION

This minimally invasive procedure Kshar Sutra has good potential in the management of Pilonidal sinus. It minimizes rates of complication and recurrence and enables the patient to resume work and normal social activities as early as possible. It is an acceptable treatment to the patient in terms of cost of treatment, extent of discomfort, impact upon body image and self-esteem.

Probable mode of action of kshara sutra

1. Pressure factor, helps in cut through of sinus tract
2. Effective drainage of pus helps to remove all contaminants & debris from tract leads to wound healing.
3. Act as chemical curettage due to presence of anti-inflammatory & anti slough agents.
4. Antibacterial
5. It prevents bleeding during procedure due to sclerosing effect of kshara by its protein coagulation property.
6. Alkalinity of kshara prevents rectal pathogens to invade the cavity.

CONCLUSION

Pilonidal sinus categorized under shalyaja nadi vrana, can cause significant discomfort and recurrence. Kshara sutra therapy is highly effective treatment modality for pilonidal sinus. It avoids the need for hospitalization and has minimal recurrence when combined with lifestyle and hygiene practices.

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